

Clinical Study on the efficacy of Auriculotherapy in the treatment of Dysmenorrhea

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Abstract

Objective: The Clinical Study to determine the efficacy of Auriculotherapy in the treatment of Dysmenorrhea

Method: (1) Auriculotherapy treatment session was done with the frequency of once a month. (2) The selected auricular points are treated with dual vaccaria seeds. (3) The applied seeds are to be maintained by the patients for a period of one month. (4) The applied individual seeds are to be pressed (stimulated) manually three time a day, by the patients. (5) The applied seeds are to be protected from the soaking of the water.

Result: All the cases benefited from the treatment. 91% cases (69/76) found completely pain free within 3 treatment sessions and 9% cases (7/76) were showed definite improvement.

Conclusion: The data suggest that the Auriculotherapy can achieve a very satisfactory, long term effect in the treatment of Dysmenorrhea. After looking at the results of the above cases, the control study may help further to get more clarity on the subject.

Keywords

Dysmenorrhea, Auriculotherapy, TCM, Acupuncture

Introduction

Dysmenorrhea means that women have pain in the lower abdomen and lower back, before, after or during menstruation which may be accompanied by dizziness, soreness of the waist, nausea, diarrhea, or even pallor, cold sweat, and cold limbs in severe cases.

Nowadays, this is a very common problem observed in young women due to the stress and change in life style including diet, exercise, sleep, & exposure to various chemical toxins in the environment.

This condition affects their learning, earning, and quality of life. When this condition is prolonged, it can cause depression.

Currently, no known easy therapy is available for treating Dysmenorrhea.

This study was conducted in Treatment Camp organized in rural village area (440 km away from Mumbai). The treatment frequency was once in a month.

General medical conditions are treated in this treatment camp. Seeing the amazing response, the retrospective study was conducted of the cases of Dysmenorrhea, which is presented herewith.

The total 76 cases were studied.

The patients in this area do not have adequate financial resources for their treatment and/or investigations. As such the conventional diagnostic investigations such as blood/hormone report, USG were not available of the subject cases. However, the diagnosis as per TCM and Auriculotherapy were performed for all the cases.

After getting astonishing results from Auriculotherapy, the patients were followed up after completion of 4 treatment sessions. Most of the patients were followed up for a period of minimum 6 months to 18 months, to ascertain the effect of the treatment.

Method

Auriculotherapy was selected as the treatment method for the cases for Dysmenorrhea since the Auriculotherapy has following salient features.

- Simple for application
- Cost effective
- No side effects
- Does not require frequent visits
- It regulates the function

The diagnosis of the patients were performed as per TCM and Auriculotherapy postulate. The following procedure is followed and based on this basis the ear points were selected and applied.

Diagnosis

Inspection:

A protruding area in the whole Uterus, Uterine Cervix, and Pelvic Cavity. (Ref. Fig.1 Inspection of Auricle - Dysmenorrhea)

Palpation:

A pressing mark in Uterus, Cervix, or Pelvic Cavity when checked with diagnostic probe.

Electrical Detection:

Positive or strong positive reactions in Uterus, Uterine Cervix, Pelvic Cavity, or Lower Jiao (Lower Warmer) when checked with Electrical Point Detector.

Fig.1 Inspection of Auricle - Dysmenorrhea

Point Selection:

Main Points: Uterus, Endocrine, Ovary, Brain Point. (Ref. Fig.2 Selection of Points - Dysmenorrhea)

Supplementary Points: Shenmen, Abdomen, Liver, Cymba Concha Center, Pelvic Cavity, Subcortex. (Ref. Fig.2 Selection of Points - Dysmenorrhea)

Fig.2. Points selection - Dysmenorrhea

Treatment Protocol

1. Auriculotherapy treatment session was done with the frequency of once a month.
2. The selected auricular points are treated with dual vaccaria seeds.
3. The applied seeds are to be maintained by the patients for a period of one month.
However, it was observed that the seeds are normally maintained for a period of 21 to 30 days after application.
4. The applied individual seeds are to be pressed (stimulated) manually three time a day, by the patients.
5. The applied seeds are to be protected from the soaking of the water.
6. The total cases registered were 76. Refer Table 1 for the differentiation of the cases based on age group

Table 1: Differentiation based on Age group

Age Group	Cases
12 - 25	21
25 - 40	46
40 & above	9
Total	76

Result

The subject 76 cases were reviewed after 4 treatment sessions and results are in Table 2.

Table 2: Results after 4 treatment sessions

No of Treatment Session	No Change in pain	Pain better up to 25%	Pain better (more than 25%)	Pain better (more than 50%)	No pain
1	23	37	12	3	1
2	13	18	25	13	7
3	0	0	22	31	23
4	0	0	2	5	69

All the cases benefited from the treatment.

91% cases (69/76) found completely pain free within 3 treatment sessions and 9% cases (7/76) were showed definite improvement.

Follow-up could be obtained from most of the cases (70/76) for a minimum of 6 months after the treatment was over.

69 (91%) cases were pain free and remaining had significant improvement in pain condition

Out of 69 cases

- 48 cases could be followed up for 18 months and they were found symptoms free.
- 17 cases could be followed up for 12 months and they were found symptoms free.

Discussion

In clinical treatment, this disease is divided into the primary referring to dysmenorrhea, which occurs in the menarche and the secondary referring to dysmenorrhea, which appears in the menstrual period after the menarche.

According to TCM, this disease is due to Qi and blood stasis in the uterus resulting from invasion of pathogenic cold or mental strain or due to deficiency of the liver and kidney, which may fail to nourish the Uterus.

Therefore dysmenorrhea can be classified into cold of deficiency type, heat of excessive type, and stagnation of Qi and blood stasis.

Point Selection:

Main Points: Uterus, Endocrine, Ovary, Brain Point.

Supplementary Points: Shenmen, Abdomen, Liver, Cymba Concha Center, Pelvic Cavity, Subcortex.

Purpose of Point Selection:

Uterus, Abdomen, Cymba Concha Center, and Pelvic Cavity: These points were selected as corresponding points to regulate and smooth the circulation of Qi to relieve pain.

Ovary, Brain Point and Endocrine: To regulate the function of the ovaries and other endocrine glands. The point Brain Point used to activate endorphins.

Kidney: For primary dysmenorrhea, this point should be selected to tone the kidney and regulate the function of Chong and Ren Channels.

Liver is a point used to relieve the depressed liver to alleviate periodic pain, since the liver channel curves around the external genitalia and enters the lower abdomen.

Sympathetic Nerve: For dysmenorrhea due to stagnation of Qi and blood stasis, this point is used to relieve spasm and alleviate pain.

Subcortex: For primary dysmenorrhea and premenstrual tension syndrome (PMS), this point can be selected to regulate the function of the cerebral cortex and relieve mental stress.

Shenmen: To tranquilize the mind and alleviate pain.

Location of Points

Uterus: This point is located at the middle of the front edge of the depression in the Triangular Fossa.

Endocrine: It is located in the inferior portion of the Cavum Concha, 0.5 cm down from the Intertragic Notch.

Ovary: It is located at the outer edge of the lateral portion of the Intertragic Notch.

Brain: It is located at center of the upper half of the interior Antitragus.

Shenmen: The line from decrease blood pressure point to pelvis is divided into three parts. It is located at the top of the first lower part.

Abdomen: It is located at the inner edge of the Antihelix corresponding to the midpoint of the Lumbar and Sacral Vertebrae.

Liver: It is located in the lateral inferior area of the Cymba Concha.

Cymba Concha Center: It is located at the center of the Cymba Concha.

Pelvic Cavity: It is located at the corner of the Triangular Fossa where the upper and lower crus of the Antihelix originate.

Subcortex: It is located in the lower half area of the interior Antitragus, at the medial side of the interior wall of the Antitragus.

Conclusion

After 4 treatment sessions, out of total 76 patients,

- 91% (69/76) patients were free from pain,
- 6% (5/76) patients got more than 50% relief,
- 3% (2/76) patients got more than 25% relief.

The data suggest that the Auriculotherapy can achieve a very satisfactory, long term effect in the treatment of Dysmenorrhea.

After looking at the results of the above cases, the control study may help further to get more clarity on the subject.

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References

1. Auricular Medicine by Dr. Li-Chun Huang
2. Auricular Points by W. Huang and L. Huang
3. Functions of the Auricular Points by W. Huang and L. Huang